

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/391073220>

Remark on Lax–Milgram theorem

Technical Report · April 2025

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20371.39209

CITATIONS

0

READS

7

1 author:

Hiroki Yagisita

Kyoto Sangyo University

52 PUBLICATIONS 28 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Remark on Lax-Milgram theorem

Hiroki Yagisita (Kyoto Sangyo University)

In the manuscript, we note a simple fact about construction of self-adjoint operator using Lax-Milgram theorem (more narrowly, Riesz theorem). Let L and H be complex Hilbert spaces. Let J be a bounded linear operator from H to L (i.e., $\|J\|_{L(H,L)} < +\infty$). Suppose that the range of J is dense in L . (In particular, note that it includes the case where J is not injective.)

Definition (elliptic equation): Let $f \in L$. Then, there uniquely exists $u \in H$ such that for any $\varphi \in H$,

$$\langle f, J\varphi \rangle_L = \langle u, \varphi \rangle_H$$

holds. So, define

$$Kf := u \in H,$$

$$Af := JKf \in L.$$

Proof: It is easy (by Riesz theorem). ■

Lemma: $\|K\|_{L(L,H)} \leq \|J\|_{L(H,L)}$ holds.

Proof: $\|Kf\|_H^2 = \langle f, JKf \rangle_L \leq \|f\|_L \|JKf\|_L \leq \|f\|_L \|J\|_{L(H,L)} \|Kf\|_H$ holds. ■

Lemma: $\|A\|_{L(L,L)} \leq \|J\|_{L(H,L)} \|K\|_{L(L,H)} \leq \|J\|_{L(H,L)}^2$ holds.

Proof: By Lemma, it is easy. ■

Lemma: A is a bounded self-adjoint operator in L .

Proof: By Lemma, A is bounded. $\langle f_1, Af_2 \rangle_L = \langle Kf_1, Kf_2 \rangle_H = \overline{\langle Kf_2, Kf_1 \rangle_H} = \overline{\langle f_2, Af_1 \rangle_L} = \langle Af_1, f_2 \rangle_L$ holds. ■

Lemma: Let $Kf = 0$. Then, $f = 0$ holds.

Proof: There exists a sequence $\{v_n\}_n$ in H such that $\lim_n \|Jv_n - f\|_L = 0$ holds. $\langle f, f \rangle_L = \lim_n \langle f, Jv_n \rangle_L = \lim_n \langle Kf, v_n \rangle_H = 0$ holds. ■

Lemma: Let $Af = 0$. Then, $f = 0$ holds.

Proof: By $\|Kf\|_H^2 = \langle f, Af \rangle_L = 0$ and Lemma, it is easy. ■

Theorem (elliptic operator): A^{-1} is a self-adjoint operator in L .

Proof: By Lemma, it is easy. ■

Japanese version is available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15273593>